

Appendix 2

Table 1: List of spiders recorded in Pusat Penyelidikan Pertanian Tun Razak (PPPTR), Pahang following different habitat types

Genus/Morphospecies	Forest	Oil Palm	Orchard	Recreational	Residential	Total
Agelenidae						
<i>Agelena</i> sp.	0	6	12	1	0	19
Araneidae						
<i>Anepsion</i> sp.	0	0	0	6	2	8
<i>Arachnura</i> sp.	0	0	2	0	0	2
<i>Araneus</i> sp.1	0	0	0	0	2	2
<i>Araneus</i> sp.2	0	0	3	1	0	4
<i>Araneus</i> sp.3	2	18	5	19	4	48
<i>Araneus</i> sp.4	0	2	7	0	2	11
<i>Argiope aemula</i>	0	0	4	0	0	4
<i>Argiope dang</i>	2	12	19	2	7	42
<i>Cyclosa insulana</i>	0	0	3	0	0	3
<i>Cyclosa mulmeinensis</i>	3	1	6	1	1	12
<i>Erovixia</i> sp.1	2	2	3	0	7	14
<i>Erovixia</i> sp.2	1	0	6	0	0	7
<i>Erovixia</i> sp.3	0	0	0	1	0	1
<i>Erovixia</i> sp.4	2	0	0	0	0	2
<i>Macracantha hasselti</i>	155	5	5	0	5	170
<i>Gasteracantha kuhli</i>	5	3	8	2	3	21
<i>Gasteracantha</i> sp.	5	2	4	0	1	12
<i>Neoscona</i> sp.1	0	1	0	0	0	1
<i>Neoscona</i> sp.2	0	0	0	0	1	1
<i>Neoscona</i> sp.3	0	0	0	0	2	2
<i>Triconephila antipodiana</i>	0	3	0	0	1	4
<i>Nephila kuhli</i>	0	1	0	0	0	1
<i>Nephila</i> sp.	0	0	1	0	0	1
<i>Poltys</i> sp. 1	0	1	0	0	0	1
<i>Poltys</i> sp. 2	0	1	8	0	7	16
<i>Poltys</i> sp. 3	0	1	0	0	0	1
<i>Zygiella</i> sp.1	0	0	2	7	3	12
<i>Zygiella</i> sp.2	0	2	0	12	1	15
<i>Zygiella</i> sp.3	0	3	2	0	0	5
Linyphiidae						
<i>Ceratinopsis</i> sp. 1	0	1	0	0	0	1
<i>Ceratinopsis</i> sp. 2	1	1	3	0	0	5
<i>Bathypanthes</i> sp.	2	1	1	0	0	4
Lycosidae						
<i>Pardosa</i> sp.	2	3	0	0	0	5
<i>Zoica</i> sp.	2	1	0	0	0	3
Oxyopidae						
<i>Oxyopes birmanicus</i>	2	12	14	4	3	35
<i>Oxyopes</i> sp.	1	0	3	2	3	9
Salticidae						
<i>Bavia</i> sp.	0	2	1	2	1	6
<i>Myrmarachne</i> sp.1	0	0	1	0	0	1

Genus/Morphospecies	Forest	Oil Palm	Orchard	Recreational	Residential	Total
<i>Omoedus</i> sp.	0	0	0	1	0	1
<i>Phaeacius malayensis</i>	0	0	1	0	0	1
<i>Plexippus</i> sp.	0	0	1	0	0	1
<i>Thiania</i> sp.1	1	0	2	0	0	3
<i>Thiania</i> sp.2	3	0	0	10	1	14
<i>Thiania</i> sp.3	0	1	0	0	0	1
Sparassidae						
<i>Heteropoda</i> sp.1	0	1	0	0	0	1
<i>Heteropoda</i> sp.2	4	4	2	0	0	10
<i>Heteropoda</i> sp.3	0	0	2	1	0	3
<i>Heteropoda</i> sp.4	1	0	1	0	0	2
<i>Heteropoda</i> sp.5	1	0	1	0	0	2
<i>Olios</i> sp.	2	0	1	0	0	3
Tetragnathidae						
<i>Leucauge decorata</i>	4	29	9	12	6	60
<i>Leucauge grata</i>	127	43	39	36	14	259
<i>Tylorida</i> sp.1	53	7	6	2	5	73
<i>Tylorida</i> sp.2	17	16	0	0	0	33
<i>Tylorida ventralis</i>	24	10	15	1	15	65
Theridiidae						
<i>Meotipa spiniventris</i>	0	0	0	1	0	1
<i>Coleosoma</i> sp.	0	0	1	0	0	1
<i>Dipoena</i> sp.	0	2	1	0	0	3
<i>Latrodectus geometricus</i>	0	5	0	5	0	10
<i>Nesticodes</i> sp.	0	0	4	0	0	4
<i>Parasteatoda</i> sp.	0	0	0	3	0	3
Theridiidae sp.	0	0	14	0	0	14
Thomisidae						
<i>Phrynarachne ceylonica</i>	1	0	0	0	0	1
Uloboridae						
<i>Uloborus</i> sp.	0	1	0	0	0	1
Total number of individuals	425	199	227	132	97	1080
No. of species	27	36	41	23	24	67
No. of family	9	10	8	7	4	11

Figure 1: Dendrogram of two way-cluster analysis on the spider community in Pusat Penyelidikan Tun Razak, Pahang